

COVRIN
**SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and
Preparedness**
**One Health research integration on SARS-CoV2
emergence, risk assessment and preparedness.**

*WP1 - T1.2 Immunological SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics in domestic
and wildlife animals*

ST1.2.2 Evaluation of methods for antibody detection from animals

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***INTERLABORATORY TESTING – SARS-CoV-2 ANTIBODY
DETECTION***

Final report

1- INTRODUCTION

Antibody detection is a crucial point for the diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 in animals, because it indirectly detects current or previous SARS-CoV-2 infections. Since the first SARS-CoV-2 cases, many different serological methods have been developed, but most of them have been developed for humans. The aim of this interlaboratory test was to compare various serological methods used in different laboratories for the diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 in animals. A panel of 20 sera of different animal species with known status for SARS-CoV-2 was used to evaluate the diagnostic performance of the different tests and compare the results between laboratories when possible.

2- GENERAL INFORMATION

A panel of 20 frozen animal sera was sent to each participating laboratory to be analysed with the serological tests available in each laboratory. Two Excel files were also sent, one to the partners before starting the inter-laboratory tests to collect data on methods, target antigens, types of antibodies detected, cut-off values of each test and other useful information, and a second to the participating laboratories to send the results obtained.

3- PANEL COMPOSITION AND DESCRIPTION

The panel of samples for the interlaboratory testing consisted of 20 sera collected from different animal species, from single or pooled animals with different status for SARS-COV-2. Sera were prepared undiluted or at different dilutions and were heat-inactivated. A total of 500 microliters of each sample was sent frozen to each participant. The description of each serum and the expected results with the methods for detection of antibodies against N or S proteins are given in the following tables.

Table 1 – Serum description

Sample	Animal Species	Serum description
1	Cattle	Serum from a cattle naturally infected with Bovine Coronavirus collected before COVID19 period
2	Pig	Serum from a pig experimentally infected with PEDV collected before COVID19 period
3	Dog	Field dog serum collected before COVID-19 period
4	Dog	Field dog serum collected before COVID-19 period
5	Cattle	Field cattle serum negative to Bovine Coronavirus collected before COVID19 period
6	Pig	Pig experimentally infected with a SARS-CoV-2 strain kindly provided by APHA
7	Ferret	Ferret experimentally infected with a SARS-CoV-2 strain (Delta Var) kindly provided by APHA
8	Ferret	Ferret experimentally infected with a SARS-CoV-2 strain (Beta Var) kindly provided by APHA
9	Mink	Pooled mink sera from animals naturally infected with a SARS-CoV-2 virus (no variant)
10	Mink	Pooled mink sera from animals naturally infected with a SARS-CoV-2 virus (no variant)
11	Guinea pig	Guinea pig serum from animals inoculated two times with partially purified inactivated beta-CoV strain (PHEV) and collected 21 DPI

12	Rabbit	Rabbit inoculated two times with SARS-CoV-2 N recombinant protein. Sera collected 30 DPI
13	Rabbit	Serum from a rabbit inoculated two times with partially purified inactivated SARS-CoV-2 strain (no variant) and collected 21 DPI
14	Guinea pig	Guinea pig serum from animals inoculated two times with partially purified inactivated beta-CoV strain (OC43) and collected 21 DPI
15	Guinea pig	Guinea pig serum from animals inoculated two times with partially purified inactivated beta-CoV strain (Bov-CoV) and collected 21 DPI
16	Rabbit	Serum from a rabbit inoculated two times with partially purified inactivated SARS-CoV-2 strain (no variant) and collected 21 DPI
17	Mink	Pooled mink sera from animals naturally infected with a SARS-CoV-2 virus (no variant)
18	Rabbit	Serum from a rabbit inoculated two times with partially purified inactivated SARS-CoV-2 strain (no variant) and collected 21 DPI
19	Pig	Field pig sera collected before COVID-19 period
20	Pig	Field pig sera collected before COVID-19 period

Table 2 – Serum status and expected results.

Sample	Animal Species	SARS-CoV-2 Status	Dilution	ID	Expected results*				
					Abs to N protein	Abs to S protein			
						Ancestral Strain		Variants [†]	
						Tot Abs	nAbs	Tot Abs	nAbs
1	Cattle	Negative	Undiluted	C+ BCoV	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
2	Pig	Negative	Undiluted	C+ PED	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
3	Dog	Negative	1/2 (pool)	211029-316196	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
4	Dog	Negative	1/2 (pool)	322671-381341	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
5	Cattle	Negative	Undiluted	C- BCoV	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
6	Pig	Infected (ancestral strain)	1/2	RAB:8683 LOT:220221	Pos	Pos	Pos	//	//
7	Ferret	Infected (Delta Var)	1/2	Ferret Delta 010122	Pos	//	//	Pos [‡]	Pos
8	Ferret	Infected (Beta Var)	1/2	Ferret Beta 120122	Pos	//	//	Pos	Pos
9	Mink	Infected	1/4 (pool)	1	Pos	Pos	Pos	//	//
10	Mink	Infected	1/4 (pool)	2	Pos	Pos	Pos	//	//
11	Guinea pig	Negative	Undiluted	PHEV Guinea pig (S-N-D)	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
12	Rabbit	Vaccinated	Undiluted	Rabbit N-COVID 19 100620	Pos	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
13	Rabbit	Vaccinated	1/8	165	Pos	Pos	Pos	//	//
14	Guinea pig	Negative	Undiluted	OC43 Guinea pig (S-N-D)	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg

15	Guinea pig	Negative	Undiluted	BCoV Guinea pig (S-N-D)	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
16	Rabbit	Vaccinated	1/8	166	Pos	Pos	Pos	//	//
17	Mink	Infected	1/6 (pool)	2	Pos	Pos	Pos	//	//
18	Rabbit	Vaccinated	1/15	166	Pos	Pos	Pos	//	//
19	Pig	Negative	Undiluted	1	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg
20	Pig	Negative	Undiluted	2	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg	Neg

* Expected results are considered against homologous strains of SARS-CoV-2. Positive results could be observed against other variants, depending on the antigenic relationship between the strains.

° Positive results against the homologous variant

4- PARTICIPANT LABORATORIES AND CONTACT PERSONS

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5- SEROLOGICAL METHODS USED BY PARTICIPANTS

The serological methods used by the participating laboratories are classified according to the antibodies detected against the N or S proteins and the type of antibodies detected. Table 3 shows the serological methods used for interlaboratory testing. Table 4 shows other serological tests not included in the interlaboratory tests, but which may provide useful additional information. These methods were classified as other tests because they provided inconclusive preliminary results, or were only validated for human sera or provided other results, such as positivity to other coronaviruses.

Table 3 – Serological methods used by the participant laboratories included in the interlaboratory testing

Antigen	Antibody type	Company	Test	Notes	Cut-off
N protein	Total Abs	Innovative Diagnostics	ID-Screen SARS-CoV-2 Multispecies double antigen ELISA	Multispecies conjugate -hrp provided by the manufacturer	P:S/P%≥60% D: 50%<S/P%<60%
N protein	Total Abs	In house	IZSLER Double-antigen N ELISA	Moreno et al., Viruses 2022, 14(8), 1738; https://doi.org/10.3390/v14081738	S/P%≥10
S1 protein (RBD)	Ig G	In house	Indirect S-based multispecies ELISA	Wernike et al., Transbound Emerg Dis. 2021,68(4):1779-1785. doi: 10.1111/tbed.13926	OD>3
S protein (S1+S2)	Ig G	In house	Indirect ELISA (recombinant SARS-CoV-2 spike)	mixture of Protein-A and G-HRPO conjugate; Complete S protein (https://www.sinobiological.com/recombinant-proteins/2019-ncov-cov-spike-40589-v08b1)	AS≥2 weakly positive; AS≥4 positive
S protein (S1+S2)	Ig G	In house	indirect ELISA species-specific HRP detection	Species specific HRP detection. Complete S protein (https://www.sinobiological.com/recombinant-proteins/2019-ncov-cov-spike-40589-v08b1)	AS≥2 weakly positive; AS≥4 positive
S1 protein	Ig G	Eurofins	INgezim® COVID 19 S VET (indirect) Prot A/G-hrp	For animal sera; https://ingenasa.eurofins-technologies.com/media/10751/ft-ei-10cosk1-ingezim-covid-19-s-vet_080721.pdf	OD>0,254
S1 protein (RBD)	Total Abs	Beijing Wantai Biological Pharmacy Enterprise	SARS-CoV-2 Total Ab Elisa	https://www.fda.gov/media/140929/download	A/CO>1 (CO=ODneg+0,16)
S protein (RBD)	Total Abs	In house	IZSLER Double-antigen S ELISA	Validation in progress	S/P%≥10
S protein (RBD)	Total Neutralising Abs	GenScrip Biotech Corporation	cPass™ SARS-CoV-2Neutralizing Antibody detection kit	Tan et al., Nat Biotechnol 2020, 38, 1073-1078, https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-020-0631-z	P:% inhibition >30
S protein (RBD)	Total Neutralising Abs	Euroimmun	SARS-CoV-2 NeutralISA	https://www.coronavirus-diagnostics.com/documents/Indications/Infections/Coronavirus/EI_2606_D_UK_F.pdf	P: % inhibition ≥ 35 Borderline: %I _{H20} to <35
SARS-CoV-2 (nextclade20C)	Total Neutralising Abs	In house	SARS-CoV-2 Virus neutralisation assay	Two-fold serial dilutions (from 1/10); 100 TCID50 of the SARS-CoV-2; virus neutralization titer 50%; Rijkers et al. J Infect Dis 2020, 1265. doi:10.1093/infdis/jiaa463	VNT50≥ 1/10
Ancestral SARTS-CoV-2 Strain	Total Neutralising Abs	In house	SARS-CoV-2 Virus neutralisation assay	Two-fold serial dilutions (from 1/4); 100 TCID50 of the SARS-CoV-2; virus neutralization titer 50%; VNT is calculated with the Spearman-Kärber method.	Reciprocal titer > 1,41
Omicron SARS-CoV-2 variant	Total Neutralising Abs	In house	SARS-CoV-2 Virus neutralisation assay	Two-fold serial dilutions (from 1/4); 100 TCID50 of the SARS-CoV-2; virus neutralization titer 50%; VNT is calculated with the Spearman-Kärber method.	Reciprocal titer > 1,41

Table 4 – Other serological assays for which results are shown but which were not included in the interlaboratory testing

Kit N.	Method	Antigen	Antibody type	Company	Test	Notes	Cut-off
A	ELISA	S1 protein (RBD)	Early Abs	Eurofins	INgezim® COVID RBD-DR	For Human sera; https://ingenasa.eurofins-technologies.com/media/12447/technical-sheet-ingezim-covid-rbd-dr_en_281021-ce.pdf . Peroxidase conjugated human IgG-specific monoclonal antibody and peroxidase-conjugated recombinant SARS-CoV-2 S protein fragment RBD.	S/P≥2,5
B	LFD	S1 protein	IgG/IgM	Spark Diagnostics	CoV-Check - Covid-19 Nab Test	For Human sera; https://sparkdiagnostics.com/cov-check/	Test line
C	VNT	BoVCoV	Total Neutralising Abs	In house	BoVCoV virus neutralisation assay	A fixed concentration of serum (1:50) was tested with 3 ascending BCV concentrations (100, 1000 and 10.000 TCID50 per M24 well). Neutralization index (NI) expressed as the concentration of virus completely neutralized by a 1:50 dilution of the test serum. All sera were pre-heated for 30 min at 56°C before testing.	NI>100
D	VNT	TGEV	Total Neutralising Abs	In house	TGEV virus neutralisation assay	A fixed concentration of serum (1:50) was tested with 3 ascending TGEV concentrations (100, 1000 and 10.000 TCID50 per M24 well). Neutralization index (NI) expressed as the concentration of virus completely neutralized by an 1:50 dilution of the test serum. All sera were pre-heated for 30 min at 56°C before testing.	NI>100
E	ELISA	N protein	IgG	In house	Indirect Multispecies ELISA N	Not validated	OD>3

6- RESULTS

The results are divided into different tables according to the kits used by the participating laboratories to facilitate the comparison of results between laboratories:

- ELISA test for detection of antibodies against protein N, quantitative and qualitative results (Table 5);
- ELISA test for detection of antibodies against protein S, quantitative and qualitative results (Tables 6, 7);
- ELISA test for detection of neutralising antibodies against S1 protein RBD (surrogate VNT), quantitative and qualitative results (Table 8);
- Virus neutralisation tests with different antigens (SARS-CoV-2 no variants and Omicron variant), quantitative and qualitative results (Table 9);

Table n. 5 – Qualitative and quantitative results of N tests. Blue: results consistent with expected outcomes; red: results inconsistent with expected outcomes

Participant laboratories			Qualitative results			Quantitative results		
Tests used			L2	L4	L5	L2	L4	L5
			KIT 1	KIT 1	KIT 2	KIT 1	KIT 1	KIT 2
N-ELISAs		Expected results	ID-Screen SARS-CoV-2 Multispecies double antigen ELISA	ID-Screen SARS-CoV-2 Multispecies double antigen ELISA	Double-antigen N ELISA	ID-Screen SARS-CoV-2 Multispecies double antigen ELISA	ID-Screen SARS-CoV-2 Multispecies double antigen ELISA	Double-antigen N ELISA
Sample	Animal Species	Abs to N protein	P: S/P% ≥ 60% D: 0% < S/P% < 60%	P: S/P% ≥ 60% D: 0% < S/P% < 60%	S/P% > 10	P: S/P% ≥ 60% D: 0% < S/P% < 60%	P: S/P% ≥ 60% D: 0% < S/P% < 60%	S/P% > 10
1	Cattle	N	N	N	N	21	6	5
2	Pig	N	N	N	N	19	6	4
3	Dog	N	N	N	P	5	4	15
4	Dog	N	P	N	N	400	6	7
5	Cattle	N	N	N	N	7	0	5
6	Pig	P	N	N	P	28	3	14
7	Ferret	P	P	P	P	1290	596	86
8	Ferret	P	P	P	P	179	85	28
9	Mink	P	P	P	P	143	133	31
10	Mink	P	P	P	P	158	158	38
11	Guinea pig	N	P	N	N	288	1	4
12	Rabbit	P	P	P	P	1457	604	117
13	Rabbit	P	P	P	P	1185	614	128
14	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	-4	5	4
15	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	-1	3	4
16	Rabbit	P	P	P	P	1139	607	131
17	Mink	P	P	P	P	79	93	28
18	Rabbit	P	P	P	P	1182	609	124
19	Pig	N	N	N	N	12	9	9
20	Pig	N	N	N	N	3	3	5

Table n. 6 – Qualitative results of S tests. Blue: results consistent with expected outcomes; red: results inconsistent with expected outcomes

Participant laboratories				L1		L3	L4	L5		
Tests used				KIT 4	KIT 5	KIT 3	KIT 6	KIT 6	KIT 7	KIT 8
S- ELISAs		Expected results		Indirect-EL S1+S2prot-protA/G- Hrp	Indirect-EL S1+S2prot-Species- specific-Hrp	Indirect-EL S1(RBD)- multispecies-Hrp	INgezim®COVID 19 S VET (indirect) Prot A/G-hrp	INgezim®COVID 19 S VET (indirect) Prot A/G-hrp	Wantai SARS- CoV-2(RBD) Double-Ag EL	S(RBD) Double- Ag ELISA
Sample	Animal Species	SARS-CoV-2 (no var)	Variants	*AS≥2 weakly positive; AS≥4 positive	*AS≥2 weakly positive; AS≥4 positive	OD >0,3	OD > 0,254	OD > 0,254	A/0,19>1	S/P%>1
1	Cattle	N	N	N	P	N	N	N	N	N
2	Pig	N	N	N	weakly positive	N	N	N	N	N
3	Dog	N	N	weakly P	weakly positive	P	N	N	N	N
4	Dog	N	N	N	P	N	N	N	N	N
5	Cattle	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
6	Pig	P	//	weakly P	P	questionable	P	P	P	P
7	Ferret	//	P	weakly P	P	N	P	P	P	P
8	Ferret	//	P	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
9	Mink	P	//	N	P	P	N	N	P	P
10	Mink	P	//	N	P	P	P	N	P	P
11	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
12	Rabbit	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
13	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
14	Guinea pig	N	N	N	weakly positive	questionable	N	N	N	N
15	Guinea pig	N	N	weakly P	P	questionable	N	N	N	N
16	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
17	Mink	P	//	N	P	questionable	N	N	P	P
18	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
19	Pig	N	N	N	weakly positive	P	N	N	N	N
20	Pig	N	N	N	weakly positive	P	N	N	N	N

*AS=Absorbance summation factor; sum of extinctions measured at all tested serum dilutions (<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0198528#pone-0198528-g001>)

In house Indirect ELISAs

Commercial Indirect ELISAs

Double-Ag ELISAs

Table n. 7 – Quantitative results of S tests

Participant laboratories				L1		L3	L4	L5		
Tests used				KIT 4	KIT 5	KIT 3	KIT 6	KIT 6	KIT 7	KIT 8
S- ELISAs		Expected results		Indirect-EL S1+S2prot-protA/G- Hrp	Indirect-EL S1+S2prot-Species- specific-Hrp	Indirect-EL S1(RBD)- multispecies-Hrp	INgezim®COVID 19 S VET (indirect) Prot A/G-hrp	INgezim®COVID 19 S VET (indirect) Prot A/G-hrp	Wantai SARS-CoV- 2(RBD) Double- Ag EL	S(RBD) Double-Ag ELISA
Sample	Animal Species	SARS-CoV-2 (no var)	Variants	*AS≥2 weakly positive; AS≥4 positive	*AS≥2 weakly positive; AS≥4 positive	OD >0,3	OD > 0,254	OD > 0,254	A/0,19>1	S/P%>1
1	Cattle	N	N	1,11	4,38	0,01	0,099	0,085	0,1	-0,047
2	Pig	N	N	0,79	2,98	0,17	0,094	0,073	0,0	-0,038
3	Dog	N	N	2,08	2,02	3	0,148	0,105	0,2	-0,026
4	Dog	N	N	1,36	5,27	-0,14	0,111	0,087	0,1	-0,003
5	Cattle	N	N	0,28	0,57	0,01	0,049	0,054	0,2	-0,021
6	Pig	P	//	2,74	6,73	0,39	0,958	0,664	20,6	1,248
7	Ferret	//	P	2,11	6,71	0,11	0,303	0,254	17,5	0,936
8	Ferret	//	P	0,53	1,65	0,02	0,077	0,070	0,2	0,049
9	Mink	P	//	0,87	13,36	0,46	0,182	0,170	20,6	2,23
10	Mink	P	//	0,90	13,57	0,76	0,343	0,195	20,7	2,354
11	Guinea pig	N	N	0,30	1,77	0,03	0,098	0,066	0	0
12	Rabbit	N	N	0,66	1,75	-0,03	0,108	0,110	0,1	-0,06
13	Rabbit	P	//	10,74	12,82	3,75	3,963	3,776	20,6	3,886
14	Guinea pig	N	N	0,33	2,50	0,31	0,070	0,080	0	0
15	Guinea pig	N	N	2,58	12,40	0,38	0,077	0,099	0	0
16	Rabbit	P	//	12,38	13,53	3,54	5,025	3,877	20,3	4,091
17	Mink	P	//	0,73	12,35	0,3	0,128	0,122	20,7	1,775
18	Rabbit	P	//	10,02	11,95	3,63	4,075	3,878	20,5	3,945
19	Pig	N	N	0,89	2,82	2,93	0,199	0,169	0,1	-0,022
20	Pig	N	N	0,77	2,94	2,81	0,174	0,172	0,1	-0,027

*AS=Absorbance summation factor; sum of extinctions measured at all tested serum dilutions (<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0198528#pone-0198528-g001>)

Table n. 8 – Qualitative and quantitative results of sVNT. Blue: results consistent with expected outcomes; red: results inconsistent with expected outcomes.

Participant laboratories				Qualitative results				Quantitative results			
Tests used				L3	L3	L4	L5	L3	L3	L4	L5
Neutralising Ab-ELISAs (surrogate VNT)		Expected results		KIT 10	KIT 9	KIT 9	KIT 9	KIT 10	KIT 9	KIT 9	KIT 9
Sample	Animal Species	SARS-CoV-2 (no Var)	Variants	Euroimmune SARS-CoV-2 NeutraLISA	GenScript cPass™ SARS-CoV-2 Neutralizing Antibody detection kit	GenScript cPass™ SARS-CoV-2 Neutralizing Antibody detection kit	GenScript cPass™ SARS-CoV-2 Neutralizing Antibody detection kit	Euroimmune SARS-CoV-2 NeutraLISA	GenScript cPass™ SARS-CoV-2 Neutralizing Antibody detection kit	GenScript cPass™ SARS-CoV-2 Neutralizing Antibody detection kit	GenScript cPass™ SARS-CoV-2 Neutralizing Antibody detection kit
				% inhibition >20 D % inhibition ≥35 P	% inhibition >30%	% inhibition >30%	% inhibition >30%	% inhibition >20 D % inhibition ≥35 P	% inhibition >30%	% inhibition >30%	% inhibition >30%
1	Cattle	N	N	N	N	N	N	-18	1	3	8
2	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	N	-25	-2	6	12
3	Dog	N	N	N	N	N	N	-27	-6	10	11
4	Dog	N	N	N	N	N	N	-36	-4	11	7
5	Cattle	N	N	N	N	N	N	-30	-1	5	6
6	Pig	P	//	P	P	P	P	52	80	83	83
7	Ferret	//	P	P	P	P	P	79	79	78	82
8	Ferret	//	P	N	N	N	N	-20	-2	8	25
9	Mink	P	//	P	P	P	P	78	83	84	89
10	Mink	P	//	P	P	P	P	76	85	88	89
11	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	N	-27	5	7	9
12	Rabbit	N	N	N	N	N	N	-34	5	12	19
13	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	P	98	97	93	97
14	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	N	-12	10	15	10
15	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	N	-22	-1	11	7
16	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	P	98	97	93	98
17	Mink	P	//	P	P	P	P	47	70	76	72
18	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	P	98	97	93	97
19	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	N	-2	1	1	6
20	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	N	-30	-2	9	12

Table n. 9 – Qualitative and quantitative results of cVNT. Blue: results consistent with expected outcomes; red: results inconsistent with expected outcomes.

Participant laboratories				L 2		L5	L 2			L5			
tests used				KIT 11	KIT 11	KIT 11	KIT 11			KIT 11			
cVirus neutralisation Tests		Expected results		cVNT SARS-CoV-2 (ancestral)	cVNT SARS-CoV-2 (omicron)	cVNT SARS-CoV-2 (nextclade20C)	cVNT SARS-CoV-2 (ancestral)			cVNT SARS-CoV-2 (omicron)		cVNT SARS-CoV-2 (nextclade20C)	
Sample	Animal Species	SARS-CoV-2 (no Var)	Variants	P> 1.41 (reciprocal titre)	P> 1.41 (reciprocal titre)	VNT50% D>1/5 P> 1/10	Serum dilution	Wells	P> 1.41 (reciprocal titre)	Serum dilution	Wells	P> 1.41 (reciprocal titre)	VNT50% D>1/5 P> 1/10
1	Cattle	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
2	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
3	Dog	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
4	Dog	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
5	Cattle	N	N	P	N	N	1/4	8	11,31	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
6	Pig	P	//	P	P	P	1/8	6	16	1/1	7	2,38	1/10
7	Ferret	//	P	N	P	D	1/1	4	1,41	1/32	4	45,25	1/5
8	Ferret	//	P	Weak P	N	N	1/1	5	1,68	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
9	Mink	P	//	Weak P	P	P	1/1	8	2,83	1/4	4	5,66	1/20
10	Mink	P	//	P	Weak P	P	1/64	4	90,51	1/1	8	2,83	1/80
11	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
12	Rabbit	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
13	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	1/128	4	181,02	1/16	7	38,05	1/320
14	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
15	Guinea pig	N	N	N	Weak P	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	5	1,68	<1/5
16	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	1/128	4	181,02	1/128	4	181,02	1/320
17	Mink	P	//	P	Weak P	P	1/16	9	53,82	1/1	6	2	1/40
18	Rabbit	P	//	P	P	P	1/32	7	76,11	1/4	6	8	1/160
19	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5
20	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	1/1	4	1,41	1/1	4	1,41	<1/5

Table n. 10 – Quantitative and qualitative results obtained with the other tests.

Sample	Animal Species	Expected results					L3				L5		L1			
		Abs to N protein	Abs to S protein				N test		S test		S test		BCV (whole virus)		TGEV (whole virus)	
			SARS-CoV-2 (no Variants)		SARS-CoV-2 Variants		KIT E		KIT B		KIT A		KIT C		KIT D	
			Tot Abs	nAbs	Tot Abs	nAbs	Indirect Multispecies ELISA N Prot A/G-hrp	CoV-Check - Covid-19 Nab Test (S antigen)	INgezim® COVID RBD-DR	BCV cvNT	TGEV cvNT					
				>0,3 OD	Qualitative	Test line	Qualitative	S/P≥2,5	Qualitative	NI >100	Qualitative	NI>100	Qualitative			
1	Cattle	N	N	N	N	N	0,57	P		N	-0,05	N	10000	P	0	N
2	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	0,9	P		N	-0,10	N	0	N	0	N
3	Dog	N	N	N	N	N	0,45	P		N	-0,10	N	0	N	0	N
4	Dog	N	N	N	N	N	0,18	N		N	-0,08	N	10000	P*	100	P*
5	Cattle	N	N	N	N	N	0,02	N		N	-0,10	N	0	N	0	N
6	Pig	P	P	P	//	//	0,11	N		N	7,87	P	0	N	0	N
7	Ferret	P	//	//	P	P	0,11	N		N	1,53	N	0	N	0	N
8	Ferret	P	//	//	P	P	0,06	N		N	0,39	N	0	N	0	N
9	Mink	P	P	P	//	//	0,12	N		N	2,52	P	0	N	0	N
10	Mink	P	P	P	//	//	0,16	N		N	9,06	P	0	N	0	N
11	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	0,03	N		N	-0,05	N	100	P	0	N
12	Rabbit	P	N	N	N	N	2,91	P		N	-0,07	N	0	N	0	N
13	Rabbit	P	P	P	//	//	3,88	P	2,75301	P	34,51	P	0	N	0	N
14	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	0,06	N		N	-0,05	N	1000	P	0	N
15	Guinea pig	N	N	N	N	N	0,08	N		N	-0,05	N	10000	P	0	N
16	Rabbit	P	P	P	//	//	3,77	P	2,80637	P	38,09	P	0	N	0	N
17	Mink	P	P	P	//	//	0,08	N		N	1,96	N	0	N	0	N
18	Rabbit	P	P	P	//	//	1,46	P	2,83871	P	36,92	P	0	N	0	N
19	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	0,42	P		N	-0,01	N	0	N	0	N
20	Pig	N	N	N	N	N	0,84	P		N	-0,03	N	0	N	0	N

* Field dog sera (pool). No information is available on positivity to other coronaviruses.

7- CONCLUSIONS

The participating laboratories used a wide variety of serological methods. These methods differed in terms of the target antibodies (against N, complete S, S1 or RBD of the S1 protein), the type of antibody detected (total Abs, IgG, IgM, neutralising Abs (nAbs)), the type of test (indirect or double-antigen ELISAs, surrogate viral neutralisation tests (sVNT) and cellular viral neutralisation tests (cVNT)) and finally by commercially available or in-house tests. Five laboratories participated in the interlaboratory testing with 16 different tests, making it extremely difficult to compare results between laboratories. Only 11 tests were included in the comparison of results, while the other five kits were reported in a separate table to provide only additional information.

The characteristics of the 11 tests included in the comparison of results are summarised below:

Detection of N-Abs

- Two double-antigen ELISAs (1 commercial + 1 in-house)

Detection of S-Abs

- Three in-house indirect ELISAs and one commercial ELISA, which differed in the antigen and HRP-conjugate used. The antigens used were RBD-S1, S1 or complete S proteins (S1+S2). Different HRP-conjugates were also used, such as protein A/G, species-specific or commercial multi-species conjugates.
- Two double-antigen ELISAs using both RBD-S1 proteins (1 commercial + 1 in-house).
- Two commercial ELISAs for the detection of nAbs, called surrogate virus neutralisation tests (sVNT).
- Virus neutralisation tests (cVNT) using different antigens, serum dilutions and expression results.

Comparison of the results obtained by each participant with the expected outcomes revealed a better diagnostic performance for some S-Abs tests than for N-Abs tests. Different diagnostic performance was observed with S-Abs tests depending on the type of ELISA used, antigen or HRP conjugate. Indirect ELISAs, in particular internal ELISAs, showed a lower diagnostic performance. The type of antigen may have led to a decrease in specificity, as the use of the full S protein may cause cross-reactions with sera positive for other

coronaviruses. The type of conjugate used also resulted in different performance. In particular, there was a decrease in sensitivity of tests using prot A/G-HRP with mink sera, probably due to a lower binding capacity between prot A/G and mink serum. Double-antigen ELISAs, both commercial and in-house, provided excellent diagnostic performance in terms of both sensitivity and specificity, but only one laboratory used these tests, so only a qualitative assessment of results against expected outcomes was possible. Two different sVNT were used by three different laboratories and, since both tests have similar cut-off, it was possible to compare the quantitative results between participants and the qualitative results against the expected results. Very good results were obtained in terms of both quantitative and qualitative results. Also good diagnostic performance for the cVNT assays were observed even if different antigens, serum dilutions and expression results were used.

In conclusion double-Antigen ELISAs, sVNT and cVNT assays able to detect anti-S Abs showed better diagnostic performance and reliability for testing animal sera for SARS-CoV-2. However, we can expect a reduced sensitivity of these tests when Abs eventually presented in the serum are to antigenically distant S-antigens (variants) of SARS-CoV-2. ELISAs for detection of N-Abs were instead able to detect Abs also against SARS-CoV-2 variants. This problem could be solved for the surrogate sVNT by testing serum with S1-RBD-HRPs of different SARS-CoV-2 variants in parallel but this can be costly, especially when it is not clear against which variant antibodies should be tested. cVNT can also be performed using different strains of SARS-CoV-2, but is time consuming and labour intensive, must be performed in a BSL-3 laboratory, and usually takes 2-4 days to complete. For these reasons, this method may not be suitable for large-scale serological diagnosis.

Based on these results we conclude that a good compromise for surveillance of animal sera could be ELISA screening for the detection of antibodies against the N protein, which are also able to detect antibodies against the SARS-CoV-2 variants, although the sensitivity is lower than some methods for the detection of S-Abs. Finally, confirmation of positive samples with other tests (sVNT or cVNT using different SARS-CoV2 antigens).